

Glossary

Accountability (in AI)

Accountability means being clear about who is responsible for decisions made by AI systems and what happens if something goes wrong.

Example

It is like knowing who to contact and what will happen if there is a problem, instead of being passed around.

Accountability means people taking responsibility when something goes wrong.

Algorithm

Algorithms are programmed step by step instructions that tell a computer how to process information and produce a result. They are used to sort data, find patterns, or support decisions.

Example

Like following a recipe where each step leads to the next until the final result.

An algorithm is a list of steps that tells a computer what to do.

Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to computer systems designed to carry out tasks that usually require human thinking, such as recognising patterns, learning from experience, or supporting decisions.

Example

Online shops, like Amazon, sometimes suggesting products you might like based on what you previously bought.

AI is when computers are designed to mimic aspects of human processing.

This glossary is designed to support you in meetings, workshops, and conversations about data and AI.

*Each page includes a definition, an example and a short summary (top right bubble) to help explain the term. **You can also use the back of each page to make your own notes.***

*This is a growing resource. **You can add new terms by using the blank pages, writing your own notes, or printing and inserting new glossary cards into your binder.***

*There is also **space to note down unfamiliar terms**, which can help shape future versions of this glossary.*

Make it your own, use it in the way that works best for you!

Notes

Notes

Notes

Bias (in AI)

Bias (in AI) happens when an AI system produces unfair results because it is trained on non-inclusive data or designed in ways that do not consider everyone. This can mean some groups are treated less accurately or less fairly than others.

Example

If a music app is trained mostly on one type of music, it may keep recommending the same style and ignore other tastes, even when people want variety.

Bias is when patterns in programming lead to unfair outcomes.

Big Data

Big data helps researchers and professionals understand trends that would be impossible to see at an individual level, for example, spotting early warning signs of health problems across large groups.

Example

When health data from millions of people is analysed together, researchers can see trends or early warning signs of disease that would not be visible when looking at one person at a time.

Big data is the analysis of large, multi-source datasets to uncover patterns and insights

CDSS

Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) are digital tools that help healthcare professionals make decisions by providing reminders, alerts, or evidence based suggestions.

Example

It is like a spell check tool that highlights possible mistakes but lets the writer decide what to change.

CDSS helps doctors and nurses make decisions.

Chatbots (ChatGPT, Claude etc)

Chatbots are computer programs that simulate conversations, answering questions or providing information automatically, often using rules or AI models.

Example

It's like a website chat box, but tools like ChatGPT or Claude can hold longer conversations and provide more detailed explanations.

Chatbots are systems that talk to people using text or voice.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

Clustering

Clustering is a method used in data analysis to group similar pieces of information together based on shared features.

Example

It is like sorting laundry into piles of whites, colours, and darks before washing.

Clustering means putting similar things into groups.

CPRD

Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) is a research service that provides access to de-identified health data from a network of over 2,400 UK GP practices. The data come from routine clinical records and are used to support public health research.

Example

It is like a large library of health records where personal information is removed so patterns can be studied.

CPRD is a secure source of health data for research.

Continuous learning system

A continuous learning system is a system that updates and improves over time as new data becomes available, instead of staying fixed.

Example

It is like a navigation app that gets better at suggesting routes as more people use it.

A continuous learning system learns and improves over time.

Dashboard

A dashboard is a visual display that brings together key information so it can be understood at a glance.

Example

It is like a car dashboard that shows speed, fuel level, and warning lights all together.

A dashboard shows relevant information together in one visual display, often on one screen.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

Dataset

A dataset is a structured collection of data that is grouped together so it can be analysed or used by a system.

Example

It is like a spreadsheet where each row and column stores potentially related information in one place.

A dataset is a collection of information.

Data linkage

Data linkage is the process of connecting data from different sources to create a more complete picture.

Example

It is like combining bank statements from different accounts to understand your overall spending.

Data linkage means joining information from different places.

Data into Action (DIA)

Data into Action (DIA) is a regional programme that uses health and social care data to improve services, support prevention, and deliver better outcomes for people in Cheshire and Merseyside.

Partners

Cheshire and Merseyside Integrated Care Board, Liverpool City Region Local Authority, and University of Liverpool

Data into Action uses data to improve local health and health equity

De-identification

De-identification is the process of removing information that could identify a person, so data can be used safely without revealing who it belongs to.

Example

It's like covering the name and address on a letter (redacting) before sharing the message inside , the information stays useful, but the person stays private.

De-identification
hides who the data is
about.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

Digital exclusion

Digital exclusion happens when people cannot access or use digital tools because of barriers such as cost, lack of equipment, skills, disability, or poor connectivity.

Example

It is like being asked to book an appointment online when you do not have internet access, the right device, or the confidence to use the website.

Some people cannot easily use digital services, or choose not to use them.

Digital health technology

Digital health technology includes digital tools and systems used to support health care, such as apps, online services, or monitoring devices.

Example

Like using a home blood pressure monitor or glucose monitor that records readings and helps track your health over time.

Digital health technology uses digital tools to support health.

Digital infrastructure

Digital infrastructure refers to the systems and technologies that allow data to be stored, shared, and used safely.

Example

It is like the roads, electricity, and plumbing that make a city work.

Digital infrastructure is the systems that make it possible to use data.

DynAIRx

DynAIRx is a research project using AI and digital tools to support prescribing and care for people with multiple long term conditions.

Partners

University of Liverpool, University of Leeds, University of Manchester, University of Glasgow, Mersey Care and Powys Teaching Health Board.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

EHR/EPR

Electronic health records (EHR) or electronic patient records (EPR) are digital records containing a person's medical information, including demographics, diagnoses, treatments, test results, and notes recorded during any interaction with healthcare providers.

Example

It is like an online folder that keeps test results, appointments, and notes in one place.

Electronic health records are digital health files.

Ethics (in AI)

Ethics in AI refers to the principles and responsibilities that guide how AI systems should be designed and used. These principles aim to ensure that AI is developed and applied in ways that are fair, safe, transparent, and respectful of people's privacy and rights.

Example

It is like setting clear guidelines for a service so people are treated fairly and not put at risk.

Ethics in AI means using AI in ways that follow clear principles so it is fair, safe, and responsible.

Explainability

Explainability refers to how clearly a system can show why it produced a particular result or decision.

Example

It is like seeing the working in a maths problem instead of only the final answer.

Explainability shows how and why a system made a decision.

Hallucinations (in AI)

Hallucinations in AI happen when an AI system generates information that sounds plausible but is actually incorrect or made up. This can happen when the system tries to fill gaps in its knowledge.

Example

It is like seeing a mirage in the desert. From a distance it looks like water and seems believable, but when you get closer you realise it is not real.

AI hallucinations are plausible-sounding answers that are wrong.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

Human oversight (in AI)

Human oversight means that people remain involved in monitoring, guiding, or checking AI and digital systems to ensure they are used safely and appropriately.

Example

Like a pharmacist reviewing a computer's prescription suggestions before the medicine is given to a patient.

Human oversight means people check and guide systems.

Integrated care board (ICB)

An Integrated Care Board (ICB) is an NHS organisation that plans and funds health and care services for a local area. The ICB runs the ICS for that area.

Example

It is like a local committee that manages a shared budget to make sure the community's health and care needs are met.

An integrated care board plans how services are planned and paid for locally

Integrated Care System (ICS)

An Integrated Care System (ICS) is a group of organisations working together to plan and provide health and care services for a local area.

Example

It is like different teams in a hospital, GP surgeries, and community care working together to make sure people get the care they need.

An ICS is the system that coordinates care across health and social services.

Information governance

Information governance (IG) refers to the rules, policies, and processes that ensure information is used legally, safely, and responsibly, including compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Example

It is like having clear rules about who can see personal documents and how they should be stored.

Information governance means using information safely and properly.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

Interoperability

Interoperability is the ability of different systems or organisations to share information and work together effectively.

Example

It is like using the same charger for different devices instead of needing a new one each time.

Interoperability means systems can share information.

Informed consent

Informed consent means a person clearly understands how their data or participation will be used and agrees freely.

Example

It is like agreeing to a contract only after reading and understanding the terms.

Informed consent
requires clear
understanding before
agreeing.

Large language model

A large language model (LLM) is a type of AI system trained on very large amounts of data so it can understand, generate, and respond to language.

Example

It is like someone who has read millions of books and can use that experience to answer questions or write text.

A large language model is a computer system that works with words and text.

Machine learning

Machine learning (ML) is a type of AI where systems learn patterns from data rather than being given fixed instructions.

Example

Your email service uses machine learning to learn which messages are spam and which are important, based on the kinds of emails you open or delete.

Machine learning means computers learn from examples instead of rules.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

Multiple Long-Term Conditions (MLTCs)

Multiple long-term conditions (MLTCs) refers to when a person has two or more ongoing health conditions at the same time.

Example

It is like someone having diabetes and arthritis at the same time, both of which need regular care.

MLTCs means having several health conditions together.

NLP

Natural language processing (NLP) is a field of research dedicated to how computers understand, analyse, and work with human language.

Example

It is like teaching a computer to read emails and understand what they are about.

Natural language processing helps computers understand language.

Neural network (in AI)

A neural network is a type of AI model inspired by how the human brain works, using connected layers to learn patterns in data.

Example

It is like learning by connecting ideas together, rather than memorising one fact at a time.

A neural network is a computer system that learns from connections.

Poisoning (in AI)

Poisoning in AI happens when incorrect or misleading data is added to the data used to train an AI system, which can cause the system to produce unreliable or harmful results later. This can happen intentionally or accidentally.

Example

It is like giving someone wrong instructions so they make mistakes later.

Poisoning means adding harmful information to a system.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

Polypharmacy

Polypharmacy happens when a person takes several medications at the same time.

Example

It is like a person taking pills for blood pressure, diabetes, and cholesterol every day.

Polypharmacy is when someone takes many medicines together.

Population health

Population health looks at the health outcomes of groups of people and how health is shared across a population.

Example

It is like looking at how healthy a whole town is rather than one person at a time.

Population health means the health of groups of people.

Randomisation

Randomisation is a research method that assigns people or data to different groups by chance so the results are fair and unbiased.

Example

It is like drawing names from a hat to decide who goes into which team.

Randomisation means using chance to decide which group someone is placed in.

Secure data environment (SDE)

A Secure Data Environment (SDE) is a safe digital space where sensitive data can be stored and accessed securely for approved research or analysis.

Example

Like a locked reading room where you can view important documents but cannot take them away.

TRE – term used mainly in research contexts

SDE – broader NHS/government term for secure data infrastructure

An SDE is a secure place where sensitive data can be stored and safely accessed.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

Structured medication review (SMR)

An SMR reviews medicines to ensure they are safe, current and right.

A Structured Medication Review (SMR) is a confidential appointment, usually with a clinical pharmacist, to review a patient's medicines and ensure they are safe, effective, and appropriate.

Example

It's like reviewing all your medicines with a pharmacist to check what you still need, if any clash, and whether doses should change.

Synthetic data

Synthetic data is artificially created data designed to look like real data but not linked to real people. It is often used to test systems or protect privacy.

Example

It is like artificial grass that looks real but is not made from real plants.

Synthetic data is made-up data that looks real but does not come from real people.

Service evaluation

Service evaluation is the process of formally assessing how well a service works and whether it meets its aims.

Example

It is like asking customers for feedback to see if a service needs improving.

Service evaluation checks how well a service works.

Test data/ Training data

Training data and test data are parts of a dataset used to develop AI systems. Training data teaches the system to recognise patterns, while test data checks whether it can apply what it learned to new information.

Example

It is like studying for an exam and then taking a test to see how much you learned.

Test data checks how well a system performs after being trained.

Notes

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Notes

Notes

TGCNNs

Temporal Graph Convolutional neural networks (TGCNNs) help computers learn patterns in networks that change over time.

Example

It is like predicting bus delays by watching both the route map and how the traffic changes every hour.

TGCNNs help computers learn how connections between things change over time.

Theograph

A theograph is a visual tool used to show a patients' interactions with health and social care services over time.

Example

It is like a map showing the places you visited and how they are connected.

A theograph show
how patients use
services over time.

Trusted research environment (TRE)

A Trusted Research Environment (TRE) is a secure system where researchers analyse sensitive data without downloading or copying it. The data stays inside the system and special tools are used.

Example

It is like working in a secure office where documents must stay in the room and cannot be taken outside.

TRE – term used mainly in research contexts

SDE – broader NHS/government term for secure data infrastructure

A TRE lets researchers securely analyse sensitive data without removing it.

Transparency

Transparency refers to how open and clear an organisation or system is about what it does and how decisions are made.

Example

It is like a clear window where you can see inside, instead of a blacked-out window where you cannot.

Transparency means being open and honest about how things work.

Notes

Notes

Notes

Notes

User interface (UI)

A user interface (UI) is the part of a system that people interact with, such as screens, buttons, or menus.

Example

It is like the buttons and screen on a cash machine.

A user interface is how a person uses a system.

User experience (UX)

User experience (UX) is about how a person feels when using a system, service, or product, including how easy, clear, or frustrating it is.

Example

It is like how easy or stressful it feels to use a ticket machine, not just whether it works.

User experience is how easy and comfortable something is to use.

Write down any terms you come across in meetings that could be added to future versions of this glossary.

Example

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Handwritten blue lines for writing.

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THIS GLOSSARY WAS CO-CREATED THROUGH COLLABORATION BETWEEN A DESIGNER, RESEARCHERS, AND PUBLIC ADVISORS.

DESIGNED BY:

LUKA KILLE-SPECKTER

RACHAEL WRIGHT

WITH SUPPORT FROM:

IAN [SURNAME]

LAUREN [SURNAME]

ERIN MCCLOSKEY

CO-CREATED WITH PUBLIC ADVISORS:

ALI BRYANT

PYERS SYMON

ALAN GRIFFITHS

FARHEEN YAMEEN

SAIQA AHMED

TOM

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